

Synthesis, characterization and antiviral activity of 2,3-disubstituted quinazolones

V. K. Pandey^{a*}, Jitendra Kumar^b, S. K. Saxena^a, Mukesh^a, M. N. Joshi^c and S. K. Bajpai^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226 007, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : vinodkumarpandey@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, D.N.P.G. College, Gulaothi, Bulandshahr-245 008, Uttar Pradesh, India

^cCentral Drug Research Institute, Lucknow-226 001, Uttar Pradesh, India

Manuscript received 10 August 2006, revised 10 April 2007, accepted 18 April 2007

Abstract : Anthranilic acid on reaction with excess equivalent of an aromatic acid chloride in pyridine yields 2-aryl-4-oxo-3,1-benzoxazines (1). Reaction of 1 with *p*-aminophenol in pyridine furnishes 2-aryl-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4-oxo(3*H*)-quinazolones (2) which reacts with amido-alcohols in the presence of conc. H₂SO₄ to give 3-(4-hydroxy-3-phthalimidomethyl/3-ethyl-2-phenyl-4-oxo(3*H*)-quinazoliny/1-ethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-quinoliny-phenyl)-2-aryl-4-oxo(3*H*)-quinazolin-4-ones (3). Compounds 3 have been evaluated for their antiviral activity against *Japanese encephalitis virus* (JEV) and *Herpes simplex virus type-I* (HSV-I) both *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

Keywords : Quinazolones, antiviral activity, RNA polymerase.

The designing and development of selective non-nucleoside inhibitors of virus polymerases is an emerging area of research activity¹⁻⁵. Interest in discovering non-nucleoside inhibitors of virus polymerases increased after the pronounced antiviral activity of enviroxime – which is truly selective inhibitor of RNA polymerase⁶ although other non-nucleoside benzimidazoles viz. 2-(α -hydroxybenzyl-benzimidazole) (HBB) and (*N*-methylisatin- β -thio-semicarbazone); methisazone have been widely used against RNA viruses since a long time^{7,8}. Subsequently, other synthetic compounds were developed and assayed for their antiviral activity. Amongst various synthetic compounds, quinazolones have been demonstrated to be potential candidate molecules against several strains of virus since such compounds exhibit varying degree of virus inhibition properties against *Semliki forest disease virus* (SFV)⁹, *Ranikhet disease virus* (RDV)¹⁰, *Encephalomyocarditis virus* (EMCV)¹¹, *Japanese encephalitis virus* (JEV)¹² and *Herpes simplex virus type-I* (HSV-I)¹³. Interest in quinazolone chemistry has increased many folds because of their association with varying degree of antiviral activity against animal and plant viruses¹⁴⁻¹⁷. These valid observations led the authors to undertake the synthesis of 2,3-disubstituted quinazolones 3a-f (Scheme 1) in order to study their antiviral activity

against both RNA and DNA viruses.

Results and discussion

Reaction of 2-aryl-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4(3*H*)-quinazolone (2) with amidoalcohols in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid afforded 3-[(4-hydroxy-3-phthalimidomethyl/3-ethyl-2-phenyl-4-oxo(3*H*)-quinazoliny/1-ethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxoquinoliny) phenyl]-2-aryl-4-oxo(3*H*)-quinazolines (3) in the yields ranging from 55 to 75%. These compounds 3 were characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and mass spectral data. IR spectrum of the compound 3c exhibited characteristic absorption bands at 1630, 1686 and 3325 cm⁻¹ due to imino, tertiary amido carbonyl and phenolic hydroxyl groups, respectively. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the compound 3c displayed signals at δ 7.30–7.90 for aromatic protons, one signal at 5.0 for phenolic OH proton, a triplet at δ 2.85 for methylene protons attached with the nitrogen atom. In the ¹³C NMR spectrum 3c showed signals at 168.0 and 164.6 for tertiary amido carbons, at 152.0 due to imino carbon and at 132.2, 128.6, 128.1, 127.1, 122.1, 119.0, 115.8 for aromatic carbons. In the mass spectrum of 3c, a base peak appeared at *m/z* 105.

Pharmacological activity : All the six-compounds

Scheme 1

3a-f were bioevaluated for their antiviral activity against two animal viruses viz. *Japanese encephalitis virus* (JEV) (P20778) (Table 2) and *Herpes simplex virus type-1* (HSV-I) (753166) (Table 3) originally obtained from National Institute of Virology, Pune (India). Antiviral activity was performed *in vitro* (vero cells) and *in vivo* (Swiss-albino-mice). Both the viruses, were maintained by intracerebral passages of 1-3 days old suckling Swiss albino-mice. Vero cells were maintained in minimum essential medium (MEM) (Sigma, USA) with 10% foetal bovine serum (FBS) (Gibco, USA) and 100 µg of streptomycin and 40 µg/mL of gentamycin were added. Cytotoxicity as well as antiviral assay of the compounds were performed in 96 well microtitre plates (non-clear Denmark) by the standard method¹⁸. For *in vivo* testing¹⁹, the treated and untreated mice were observed for 21 days post infection. Upon the termination of experiment the percent protection and the mean survival time (MST) in day were recorded.

Out of six compounds investigated for their anti-JEV activity only one compound showed 40% CPE inhibition *in vitro* while all the six compounds were found antivirally active against HSV-I *in vitro* varying from 20 to 56 percent. Three compounds were also found to exhibit anti-HSV-I activity *in vivo* at a dose level of 200 µg/mouse.

Table 1. Characterization data of 3-[(4-hydroxy-3-phthalimidomethyl/3-ethyl-2-phenyl-4-oxo(3*H*)-quinazoliny]/1-ethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-quinolinyl]phenyl]-2-aryl-4-oxo(3*H*)-quinazolines (**3**)

Compd.	R	R'	m.p. °C	Yield (%)	Molecular formula	Nitrogen (%)	
						Found	Calcd.
3a	Phenyl	Phthalimidomethyl	121–122	75	C ₂₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	8.82	8.87
3b	Styryl	Phthalimidomethyl	163–164	70	C ₃₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄	8.83	8.41
3c*	Phenyl	3-Ethyl-2-phenyl-4-oxo(3 <i>H</i>)-quinazoliny	139–140	65	C ₃₆ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃	9.93	9.96
3d	Styryl	3-Ethyl-2-phenyl-4-oxo(3 <i>H</i>)-quinazoliny	159–160	65	C ₃₈ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₃	9.49	9.52
3e	Phenyl	1-Ethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-quinolinyl	140–141	61	C ₃₂ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₄	8.10	8.15
3f	Styryl	1-Ethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-quinolinyl	163–164	55	C ₃₄ H ₂₇ N ₃ O ₄	8.09	8.12

*IR (KBr) (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}): 1630 (C=N str.), 1686 (tert. amide C=O), 3325 (phenolic OH str.).

*¹H NMR (CDCl₃) (δ ppm): 2.85 (2H, t, CH₂-C₆H₅, *J* 7.02 Hz), 3.53 (2H, t, CH₂-N, *J* 7.02 Hz), 5.0 (1H, s, ArOH), 7.30–7.90 (21H, m, ArH).

*¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) (δ ppm): 24.9, 44.2, 115.8, 117.5, 119.0, 122.1, 125.5, 127.1, 128.6, 132.2, 152.0, 164.0, 168.0.

*Mass (*m/z*) (FAB): 105 (base peak), 145, 247, 313, 376, 396, 445, 456.

Table 2. Anti-JEV activity data of 3-[(4-hydroxy-3-phthalimidomethyl/3-ethyl-2-phenyl-4-oxo(3*H*)-quinazoliny]l/1-ethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-quinolinyl)phenyl]-2-aryl-4-oxo(3*H*)-quinazolines (3)

Compd.	R	R'	<i>In vitro</i>			TI	% CPE inhibition	<i>In vivo</i>		Protection (%)
			Dose (µg/ml)	CT ₅₀ (µg/ml)	EC ₅₀ (µg/ml)			Dose (µg/mouse/day)	MST (days)	
3a	Phenyl	Phthalimidomethyl	500-504	500	-	-	-	-	-	-
3b	Styryl	Phthalimidomethyl	500-504	500	-	-	-	-	-	-
3c	Phenyl	3-Ethyl-2-phenyl-4-oxo(3 <i>H</i>)-quinazoliny	500-504	500	-	-	-	-	-	-
3d	Styryl	3-Ethyl-2-phenyl-4-oxo(3 <i>H</i>)-quinazoliny	500-504	500	-	-	-	-	-	-
3e	Phenyl	1-Ethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-quinolinyl	500-504	500	125	4	50	-	-	-
3f	Styryl	1-Ethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-quinolinyl	500-504	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

* = non-toxic at 500 µg/mL.

CT₅₀ = 50% cytotoxic concentration, EC₅₀ = 50% effective concentration;

T_i = therapeutic index; CPE = cytopathic effect; MST = mean survival time.

Table 3. Anti-HSV-1 activity data of 3-[(4-hydroxy-3-phthalimidomethyl/3-ethyl-2-phenyl-4-oxo(3*H*)-quinazoliny]l/1-ethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-quinolinyl)phenyl]-2-aryl-4-oxo(3*H*)-quinazolines (3)

Compd.	R	R'	<i>In vitro</i>			TI	% CPE inhibition	<i>In vivo</i>		Protection (%)
			Dose (µg/ml)	CT ₅₀ (µg/ml)	EC ₅₀ (µg/ml)			Dose (µg/mouse/day)	MST (days)	
3a	Phenyl	Phthalimidomethyl	500-504	250	7.8	12	45	-	-	-
3b	Styryl	Phthalimidomethyl	500-504	250	15.62	16	26	-	-	-
3c	Phenyl	3-Ethyl-2-phenyl-4-oxo(3 <i>H</i>)-quinazoliny	500-504	250	7.8	32	55	200	4	10
3d	Styryl	3-Ethyl-2-phenyl-4-oxo(3 <i>H</i>)-quinazoliny	500-504	250	62.5	4	55	200	4	10
3e	Phenyl	1-Ethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-quinolinyl	500-504	250	62.5	4	56	200	7	20
3f	Styryl	1-Ethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-quinolinyl	500-504	250	125	2	20	-	-	-

CT₅₀ = 50% cytotoxic concentration, EC₅₀ = 50% effective concentration;

T_i = therapeutic index; CPE = cytopathic effect; MST = mean survival time.

Experimental

The melting points of the compounds were determined in open glass capillaries in the Toshniwal melting point apparatus and therefore the recorded values are uncorrected. IR spectra in KBr were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer in region ν_{\max} 4000–400 cm^{-1} and ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker DR X 200 MHz spectrophotometer using CDCl_3 as solvent (TMS as internal standard with chemical shift in δ ppm). Mass spectrum (FAB) was recorded on Jeol SX 102/DA-600. Mass spectrometer using Argon (6 KV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas.

2-Aryl-4-oxo-3,1-benzoxazines (**1**) were prepared according to the literature methods^{20,21}. *N*-Hydroxymethylphthalimide and 7-hydroxy-4-methyl coumarin were also prepared by following literature methods^{22,23}.

2-Aryl-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4(3H)-quinazolones (**2**) : The mixture of 2-aryl-4-oxo-3,1-benzoxazine (0.05 mol) and *p*-amino-phenol (0.05 mol) in dry pyridine (50 ml) was heated under reflux for 6 h under anhydrous reaction conditions and then allowed to cool at room temperature. The reaction mixture was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid and stirred. A solid separated out which was filtered off and washed with water to remove any adhered pyridine. The crude quinazolone thus obtained was dried under vacuum and recrystallized from dilute ethanol.

2-Phenyl-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4-oxo(3H)-quinazoline : m.p. 200 °C, yield 65% (Found : N, 8.75. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ requires : N, 8.91%).

2-Styryl-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4-oxo(3H)-quinazoline : m.p. 160–161 °C, yield 61% (Found : N, 8.55. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ requires : N, 8.23%).

2-Aryl-3-(hydroxyethyl)-4-oxo(3H)-quinazolines/1-hydroxyethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-quinoline : 2-Aryl-4-oxo-3,1-benzoxazine/7-hydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin (0.05 mol) was dissolved in dry pyridine (50 ml) and stirred vigorously followed by adding β -aminoethanol (0.05 ml) in portions with constant shaking. Subsequently the resultant reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h and then allowed to cool at room temperature. It was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid (100 ml). A solid separated out which was allowed to settle down. It was filtered off and washed repeatedly with cold water (4 × 25 ml) and dried over silica gel overnight. It was recrystallized from dilute ethanol.

2-Phenyl-3-(hydroxyethyl)-4-oxo(3H)-quinazoline : m.p. 164 °C, yield 80% (Found : N, 10.55. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ requires : N, 10.53%).

2-Styryl-3-(hydroxyethyl)-4-oxo(3H)-quinazoline : m.p. 108–109 °C, yield 75% (Found : N, 9.54. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ requires : N, 9.58%).

1-Hydroxyethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-quinoline : m.p. 172–173 °C, yield 75% (Found : N, 6.10. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_3$ requires : N, 6.39%).

3-[(4-Hydroxy-3-phthalimido-methyl/3-ethyl-2-phenyl-4-oxo-(3H)-quinazoliny]/1-ethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-quinoliny]-phenyl]-2-aryl-4-oxo(3H)-quinazolines (**3**) : A mixture of **2** and *N*-hydroxymethyl-phthalimide/2-aryl-3-(hydroxyethyl)-4-(3H)-quinazoline/1-hydroxyethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-2-oxo-quinoline (0.01 mol) was dissolved in minimum quantity of conc. sulphuric acid. While dissolving, the contents were cooled and subsequently stirred for 1 h. The resultant solution was left overnight under refrigeration. A solid separated out after pouring the contents into ice cold water which was filtered off and washed with cold water repeatedly in order to remove the sulphonated products. After drying under vacuum it was recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds thus synthesized, are presented in Table 1 along with their characterization data.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head of the Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, India for providing necessary laboratory facilities and to the Director of CDRI, Lucknow, India for providing elemental, spectral and biological activity data.

References

1. B. Modzelewska-Banachiewicz and T. Kaminaka, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2001, **36**, 93.
2. I. A. Vynograd, V. A. Plastunov, M. M. Kozlovsk'kü, L. V. Benzel, G. V. Bilelska, I. M. Lozynsk'kü, I. G. Rogochü and M. D. Sholomei, *Microbiol. Z.*, 2001, **63**, 14.
3. A. A. Nikitenko, Y. E. Raifeld and T. Z. Wang, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2001, **11**, 1041.
4. P. R. Wyde, O. K. Moore-Poveda, B. O'Hara, W. D. Durg, B. Mitsner and B. E. Gilbert, *Antiviral Res.*, 1998, **38**, 34.
5. N. C. Desai, J. J. Bhatt, B. R. Shah, P. B. Trivedi and N. K. Undana, *Ind. J. Exp. Biol.*, 1996, **34**, 584.
6. G. D. Diana, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1977, **20**, 750.
7. D. Hamre, J. Bernstein and R. Donovan, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1950, **73**, 275.

Pandey *et al.* : Synthesis, characterization and antiviral activity of 2,3-disubstituted quinazolones

8. I. Tamm, H. J. Eggers, R. Baklunian, A. E. Wagner and K. Folkers, *Nature*, 1969, **223**, 785.
9. V. K. Pandey and A. K. Agrawal, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, **14**, 27.
10. V. K. Pandey, D. Mishra and A. Shukla, *Ind. Drugs.*, 1994, **31**, 532.
11. V. K. Pandey, D. Mishra, M. N. Joshi and K. Chandra, *Pharma. Res. Commun.*, 1988, **20**, 153.
12. V. K. Pandey and H. S. Negi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2002, **41**, 1978.
13. V. K. Pandey and A. Shukla, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1999, **38**, 1381.
14. A. Algarsamy, U. S. Pathak, S. N. Pandeya and D. Sriram, *Ind. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2000, **60**, 433.
15. P. Selvam, K. Vanitha, M. Chandramohan and E. DeClarcq, *Ind. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2003, **65**, 386.
16. V. K. Pandey and H. S. Negi, *Biol. Mem.*, 1999, **25**, 29.
17. V. K. Pandey, K. C. Khulbe, G. Saxena, P. Gupta and K. Chandra, *Ind. Drugs*, 1993, **30**, 513.
18. R. A. Sidwell and T. H. Huffmann, *Appl. Microbiol.*, 1971, **22**, 791.
19. R. Kant, K. Chandra, B. M. Gupta, K. B. Mathur, K. Kishore and M. M. Dhar, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1977, **65**, 314.
20. N.W. Hirwe and K. N. Rana, *Ber.*, 1939, **72**, 1346.
21. M. T. Bog and H. A. Soil, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **29**, 517.
22. S. R. Buc, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 254.
23. A. A. Shamsurin, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1941, **35**, 3994.